

Agro2Circular

D9.1 – Project management guideline & quality plan

December 2021

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

1 TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)

Deliverable No.	D9.1
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 9 – Project management and coordination activities
Tasks	T9.1 – Project coordination. Quality assurance and risk management T9.2 – Administrative and financial coordination
Lead beneficiary	CETEC
Contributing beneficiary/ies	
Due date of deliverable	31 December 2021
Actual submission date	31 December 2021

PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1	09/12/21	First draft of document
v0.2	28/12/21	Revised version based on the comments of Giuliana Folco from ICONS, Arantza Blanco from Kveloce
v1.0	28/12/21	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v1.1		First draft based upon first final version
v2.0		Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1	09/12/2021	Project management board

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Fuensanta Monzó (CETEC)	28/12/21
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó (CETEC)	28/12/21

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838

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3 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

A2C	Agro2Circular
AoM	Agenda of meeting
DoA	Description of the action
CDS	Communication & Dissemination Strategy
ExC	Exploitation committee
GA	General assembly
IPR	Intellectual property right
KPIs	Key performance indicators
MoMs	Minutes of meetings
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMB	Project management board
PM ²	P-M squared
REA	European Research Executive Agency
SP	Stakeholder panel
WPSR	Work Package Status Report
TC	Technical committee
TM	Technical manager
WP	Work Package

4 GLOSSARY

Artefacts: Artefacts are tangible outputs of project management activities, such as Work Plans, Meeting Minutes, Logs, Checklists and Reports.

Closing Phase: The Closing Phase is the final phase of the project. During this phase, project activities are completed, Lessons Learned are discussed and documented, the finished deliverables are transferred to the care, custody and control of the European Commission, and the project is administratively closed.

DoA: In an H2020 project, the description of action is a document that captures the essence of the envisaged solution in the form of high-level needs and features that gives the reader an overview of the final project deliverable(s). It includes the Project Work Plan and information regarding the project scope, cost, time and risks, as well as information such as milestones, deliverables, and project organisation and approach. The DoA contains the Project Charter and the Project Work Plan of a PM² project.

Executing Phase: The Executing Phase is the third phase in a PM² project, after Initiating and Planning. It is where the project activities are carried out as defined in the project plans and the project deliverables are produced.

Initiating Phase: The Initiating Phase is the first phase in a PM² project. Its purpose is (1) to define what the project will do (formulate the objective of the project), (2) perform some initial planning to get the project off to a good start and (3) to provide and present the necessary information to get approval for the project. In A2C the initiating phase was the preparation of the project proposal, Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

Issue: An issue is any unplanned event related to the project that has already happened and requires the intervention of the project management board.

Metric: A metric is a quantifiable value that makes it possible to measure the achievement of a project/service/deliverable/process/activity objective. Metrics should be specific, measurable, actionable, relevant, and captured at the right time.

Milestones: A milestone refers to a significant point or event in a project that receives special attention. Milestones can also be used to mark key deliverables, control points, the acceptance of final outputs and closing the project.

Monitor & Control: Monitor & Control is a group of continuous activities that spans the life of a project. These activities are focused on measuring the correct execution of the project

against the agreed baselines using key metrics like costs, time and quality indicators, and taking corrective actions if the execution goes too far off plan.

Planning Phase: The Planning Phase is the second phase of a PM² project in which the subject of the project is verified and developed into a workable plan for implementation. The various standard and specific plans for the project are created in this phase.

Project Work Plan: The Project Work Plan identifies and organises the project into deliverables, work packages, activities and tasks, needed to achieve the project objectives. It establishes a base from which to estimate the duration of the project, determine the required resources and schedule the work.

Quality Assurance: Quality Assurance (QA) is the activity of providing the evidence needed to establish the quality of work and therefore provide enough confidence that the project will satisfy the desired scope and quality requirements within its constraints.

Quality Control: Quality control is the activity of monitoring and consolidating results of Quality Assurance (QA) in order to assess compliance and performance, recommend necessary changes, and plan new or refine existing quality assurance activities

Risk: A risk is an uncertain event or set of events (positive or negative) that, if it occurs, will have an effect on the achievement of project objectives. A risk is generally measured by a combination of the likelihood (probability of the risk happening) and the size of the impact on the project.

Risk owner: The risk owner is the person accountable for the implementation of the actions derived from a specific risk assessment.

5 OBJECTIVES

The objective of this deliverable is to establish and describe the methodology, procedures, and activities of planning, organising, securing, monitoring, and managing the resources and work necessary to deliver the specific project goals and objectives in an effective and efficient way.

6 SCOPE

This project management guideline and quality plan is based on PM² methodology, a Project Management Methodology developed by the European Commission, though has been tailored to be applied for Agro2Circular project, according to the project's specific needs, and will cover

the execution phase of the project. This deliverable comprises the activities and procedures for A2C project management and quality assurance.

A2C is a three-year project whose work plan is broken down into ten work-packages, which are also broken down into several tasks, including as well eight milestones scheduled during the life cycle of the project, as explained in detail in the project DoA document.

7 APPLICABLE DOCUMENTS

The following documents have been necessary to develop the Agro2Circular project management guideline and quality plan:

1. Agro2Circular DoA, which is Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement NUMBER 101036838, and contains the details of how the action (project) will be carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
2. Agro2Circular Grant Agreement NUMBER 101036838.
3. Agro2Circular Consortium agreement.
4. PM² Project Management Methodology Guide 3.0.1, March 2021.
5. PM² Glossary based on the PM² Guide v3.0

8 PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND QUALITY PLAN

Figure 1 shows the structure of the plan which involves different activities and outputs found necessary for proper project management and quality assurance, and that will be described in the following sections

Figure 1: Structure of the project management and quality plan

9 PROJECT ORGANIZATION

The consortium organizational and management structure in the A2C project was decided during the planning phase of the project and is described in detail in the DoA, Part B of Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement (page 59) (Figure 2), according to different bodies and management positions and responsibilities.

Figure 2: A2C organizational structure

9.1 CONSORTIUM ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The consortium organisational structure is described in the section 6.3 of the Consortium Agreement

It comprises the following bodies:

General assembly (GA): Responsible for the strategic decisions and the ultimate decision-making body, composed by one representative of each consortium partner and chaired by the project coordinator.

Technical committee (TC): The supervisory body for technological issues. It coordinates technological issues and is formed by a maximum of one delegate from each partner up to a maximum of five participants and chaired by the technical manager.

Exploitation committee (ExC): Coordinates all exploitation issues via the implementation and update of the Exploitation Plan, consists of one delegate from each industrial partner (SME or Large industry) and is chaired by the outreach manager.

Project management board (PMB): Organized in six management figures responsible for the project management and coordination at different levels. As the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, they shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly.

Stakeholder panel (SP): created to bring together representatives of organizations, industrial companies and associations that are relevant for the A2C's results uptake and chaired by the systemic approach manager. This Panel will make recommendations on different aspects of the systemic approach of A2C solutions.

Ethics advisory board: Composed by UVEG and CETEC, it will lead and coordinate all ethics issues.

Depending on the issues to be discussed and solved, other partners and even external stakeholders can be invited to (temporarily or permanently) join these bodies.

9.2 PROJECT MANAGEMENT BOARD

It is composed of the following positions of responsibility:

- Fuensanta Monzó from CETEC, Project Coordinator.
- Federico Mesa from CETEC, Project Manager
- Presentación García from CTNC, Technical Manager
- Maite Ferrando from KVC, Systemic Approach Manager
- Giuliana Folco from ICONS, Outreach Manager
- WP leaders

The Project Coordinator is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority. The Project Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

10 PROJECT COORDINATION

The project coordination facilitates the project's progress by continuously exchanging information with the project team (consortium) and supporting the completion of assigned work.

The project coordination will be performed at three different levels:

- Coordination at task level by the Task leader.
- Coordination at WP level by the WP leader.
- Coordination at project level by the Project Board.

The main tools for the project coordination are the communication and information exchange within the consortium and the project management board through meetings and Web-based communication (A2C web platform).

11 COMMUNICATION MANAGEMENT

The communication media that will be used for the project are:

Email(s)

Document(s) (MS Word and/or PowerPoint...)

Meeting(s) (using meeting rooms, conference phones, video rooms...).

11.1 MEETINGS

Meetings are an important tool of communication among partners, useful also to keep track of the work done, of the decisions taken and to maintain updated the entire Consortium about the overall project progress.

11.1.1 Procedure

The chairperson is responsible for setting the meeting and preparing the agenda and minutes. Meeting must be set in the calendar of the A2C google platform, using Google Meet, adding the agenda in the description. The chairperson should notify the meeting date and send the meeting agenda in advance to give participants time to organize their agendas and prepare the information to be shared according to what is written in the Consortium Agreement (Table 1 and Table 2)

Table 1: Deadline for meeting notification

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Project Management Board	14 calendar days	7 calendar days
Technical Committee	14 calendar days	7 calendar days
Exploitation Committee	14 calendar days	7 calendar days

Table 2: Deadline for sending meeting agenda

General Assembly	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Management Board	7 calendar days
Technical Committee	7 calendar days
Exploitation Committee	7 calendar days

Any Member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda by written notification to the chairperson up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated in Table 3.

Table 3: Deadline for notification of changes in the original agenda

General Assembly	14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Management Board	2 calendar days
Technical Committee	2 calendar days
Exploitation Committee	2 calendar days

The meetings will be registered and meeting minutes uploaded on the A2C platform using the specific form prepared for that purpose. The template for the agenda and the minutes of meeting preparation can be found in Annex A. Minutes must include decisions made.

The **chairperson** shall send the accepted minutes to all the Members of the Consortium Body and the Project Coordinator. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within **15 calendar days** from sending, no Member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes.

11.1.2 Type of meetings

MEETING	Executing Kick-off Meeting
Purpose	Official kick-off of the executing phase of the project. After this meeting, the Consortium will be aware of the scope of the project, the project governance structure, the roles & responsibilities of the team members as well as the project rules.
Location	Defined by the Project Coordinator
Frequency	Once the Grant Agreement has been signed by all participants
Chairperson	Project Coordinator
Minutes by	To be defined by the Project Coordinator
Attendees	All members of the Consortium
Agenda Items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introduce the agenda; ● Presentation of participants; ● Presentation of an overview of the Project Work Plan (DoA); ● Present the organizational structure; ● Advance aspects of the project coordination, management and quality plan; platform for communication and information exchange, the Risk Management, Issue Management and Project Change Management processes, and the Quality Assurance & Control activities; ● Description of every work package. ● Agree on the team's ground rules (communication via email, meetings, phone, meeting minutes to be produced, availability, etc.); ● Allow time for any other business (questions & answers);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Summarise the discussion (decisions, actions, and risk).
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting minutes written in MS word and uploaded to A2C platform using the meeting form

MEETING	GA meetings
Purpose	Discuss strategic issues relating to the project and its progress, harmonize activities, solve potential conflicts and decide on major issues
Location	Defined by the project coordinator
Frequency	Every six months
Chairperson	Project Coordinator
Minutes by	To be defined by the Project Coordinator
Attendees	All members of the consortium
Agenda Items	<p>At least</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Progress status review (review of every WP Status by every WP leader); <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accomplishments (Current and Planned actions); Indicator review. Plans reviews Actual work vs Planned; Milestone status; Risks status Results Current deliverables status Issues & decisions status Change management: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess new change requests. Project management & Quality assurance aspects Budget review
Distribution list	All participants are invited.
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting minutes written in MS word and uploaded to A2C platform using the meeting form

MEETING	PMB meetings
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Management review meeting.
Location	Defined by the Project coordinator
Frequency	At least quarterly
Chairperson	Project Coordinator
Minutes by	Defined by the project coordinator
Attendees	Project Coordinator Technical Manager Project Manager Systemic approach Manager Outreach Manager WP leaders of ongoing WPs
Agenda Items	<p>At least</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accomplishments for this period; Problems encountered and actions taken;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Major points meriting management attention; ● Subjects to be realised until next milestone/meeting; ● Evaluation of current status with respect to project scope, project budget, project finish date; ● Status of issues/actions, decisions. ● Status of risks and related actions ● New proposed changes ● Formal approvals / Commitments ● Propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Meeting minutes written in MS word and uploaded to A2C platform using the meeting form. ● WP status reports written in MS word and uploaded to the A2 platform using the form to send documents.

MEETING	Technical committee meetings
Purpose	Discuss technical issues.
Location	Defined by the Technical Manager
Frequency	Every 3 months
Chairperson	Technical Manager
Minutes by	To be defined by the Technical Manager
Attendees	All members of the Technical Committee
Agenda Items	<p>At least</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Review of identified risk and approval of assessments and actions ● Technical issues ● Technological and scientific progress & milestones ● Propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Meeting minutes written in MS word and uploaded to A2C platform using the meeting form

MEETING	Exploitation committee meetings
Purpose	Discuss exploitation & IPR issues of the project outcomes
Location	Defined by the Outreach Manager
Frequency	To be defined by the Outreach Manager
Chairperson	Outreach Manager
Minutes by	To be defined by the Outreach Manager
Attendees	All members of the Exploitation Committee

Agenda Items	<p>At least</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exploitation plan ● IPR assessment ● Innovation monitoring ● CDS & KPIs ● Outreach local desk ● Propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Meeting minutes written in MS word and uploaded to A2C platform using the meeting form

MEETING	WP meetings
Purpose	Coordination of WP and Tasks involved
Location	Defined by the WP leaders
Frequency	At least every three months
Chairperson	WP leader
Minutes by	To be defined by the WP leaders
Attendees	At least WP leader and Task leaders
Agenda Items	<p>At least</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discuss all points of the WP status report: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Accomplishments (Current and Planned actions); ○ Plans reviews ○ Actual work vs Planned; ○ Milestone status; ○ Risks identification, assessment and response ○ Arising issues (technical, coordination, resources) ○ Results & dissemination activities
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Meeting minutes written in MS word and uploaded to A2C platform using the meeting form

MEETING	SP meetings
Purpose	Feedback from stakeholders
Location	Defined by the Systemic Approach Manager
Frequency	Twice a year
Chairperson	Systemic Approach Manager
Minutes by	To be defined by the Systemic Approach Manager
Attendees	At least Project management Board Stakeholder panel

Agenda Items	<p>At least</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Main project results ● Recommendations from the stakeholder panel on the necessary features of the project' results and systemic approach: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Market routes and implementation vehicles ○ Environmental, socio-cultural & socio-economic impact of A2C solution. ○ Policies affecting A2C solution
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Meeting minutes written in MS word and uploaded to A2C platform using the meeting form

Technical review meeting: The Project Coordinator will make the necessary arrangements for the mandatory midterm review meeting by the EC Officer and external experts.

11.2 A2C PLATFORM

A2C platform is an internal, password-restricted web-based shared working environment, a Google Work Space platform created for A2C project communication and information storage.

11.2.1 Google Platform System

A2C platform is a Google Workspace for day-to-day communication by e-mail or chat, Calendar for meeting and tasks planning, Meet for on-line meeting, Drive for information storage and a website for document uploading to A2C Drive through proper forms as well as for information consultancy and downloading. All partners have access to this platform with their organization's emails and password.

11.2.2 A2C website

All partners can access the A2C information either through the website (Figure 3) or the drive.

A2C FOR PARTNERS

ACCESS TO PUBLIC A2C DOCUMENTATION	
TITLE	LAST MODIFIED
COMMUNICATION	10 Nov Coordination A2C
DELIVERABLES	14 Oct Coordination A2C
DISSEMINATION	10 Nov Coordination A2C
DOCUMENTS	17 Jul Coordination A2C
LOGOS	17 Jul Coordination A2C
MEETINGS	27 Sept Coordination A2C

Figure 3: Access to documents through the website

Documents must always be uploaded to the drive folders, using the “Sending Docs” forms available on the website, selecting to which WP folder partners want to upload the document (Figure 4). There are also specific forms to upload the information about dissemination & communication, and meetings.

A2C DOCUMENT DELIVERY

CLICK ON THE WORK PACKAGE TO WHICH YOU WANT TO UPLOAD DOCUMENTATION		
WORK PACKAGE 1	WORK PACKAGE 2	WORK PACKAGE 3
WORK PACKAGE 4	WORK PACKAGE 5	WORK PACKAGE 6
WORK PACKAGE 7	WORK PACKAGE 8	WORK PACKAGE 9
WORK PACKAGE 10		

CLICK ON THE COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION OR MEETINGS TO WHICH YOU WANT TO UPLOAD DOCUMENTATION		
COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	MEETINGS

Figure 4: Uploading of documents through A2C website

Once the specific work package is selected, the form will pop up with all the fields that are required to be filled in. Every form will contain the important instructions for their proper filling in. The uploading of documents will be automatically recorded in an excel sheet, as an updated log list of submitted documents, which will include important fields such as type of document, date of submission, who uploaded it and the link to the document.

11.2.3 A2C Drive for information storage

A2C Drive is organized in the following folders

- 1 00 A2C general (access to every partner for reading and downloading)

2. 02 A2C Work Package folder that contains a folder for every work package and every task (access to every partner for reading and downloading)

My Drive > 02 A2C WORK PACKAGE ▾

Name ↓

 WORK PACKAGE 10

 WORK PACKAGE 9

 WORK PACKAGE 8

 WORK PACKAGE 7

 WORK PACKAGE 6

 WORK PACKAGE 5

 WORK PACKAGE 4

 WORK PACKAGE 3

 WORK PACKAGE 2

 WORK PACKAGE 1

My Drive > 02 A2C WORK PACKAGE > WORK PACKAGE 2 ▾ 👤

Name ↓

 Task 2.4

 Task 2.3

 Task 2.2

 Task 2.1

 WORK PACKAGE 2 (respuestas) 👤

 WORK PACKAGE 2 👤

 A2C_Description WP2.pdf 👤

WP leaders and Task leaders will have permission for editing in their corresponding WP and Task though **documents must be always uploaded through the website forms.**

11.2.4 Shared Calendar

There is a shared calendar to set meetings and check the activities schedules. Only the WP leaders have permission for editing the calendar.

11.2.5 Emailing

E-mails are an important tool for communication. To facilitate the seeking and organization of emails by all partners, the subject of the emails involved in the project A2C must start with A2C_WPX, so that the recipient can easily identify the project and work package to which it refers.

12 MONITORING PROJECT PERFORMANCE

The purpose of monitoring the project performance is to collect information in order to evaluate the state of the project's progress and overall health. **The Project Coordinator and Project Manager** will track the project dimensions of scope, schedule, cost and quality, monitor risks, issues and project change, and forecast their evolution for the purpose of reporting the overall project progress (project progress reports).

The project coordinator will use the baselined Project Work Plan, milestones, and WP annual work plans as a reference for monitoring the project performance, and will track the scope and schedule using the information gathered from the MoMs and WP leaders reporting (WP status reports). After receiving the WP status reports, the project coordinator will perform an internal audit of the project performance and prepare the project progress audit report where the project performance will be assessed, including project indicators and metrics for evaluating progress, conclusions, and proposed contingency measures in case any issues arise.

Internal reporting: The project coordinator will request the following inputs from the WP leaders in order to collect all the information necessary for the project progress monitoring and control:

- WP annual work plans
- Task status reports

The project manager will request financial planning and reporting from every partner:

- Budget execution planning
- Statement of financial situation.

Monitoring and control: important aspects of the project will be managed as part of the activities necessary for the project monitoring and control:

- Control of the project progress (Scope & Schedule) through internal audits.
- Management of issues and decisions
- Management of changes
- Management of risks

12.1 WP ANNUAL PLANS

The project DoA includes the project Gantt and scheduled milestones, with a detailed description of the objectives and work to be done in every work-packages and sub-tasks. To

assure the proper performance of all project works, every **WP leader** must prepare, together with the task leaders, a WP annual work plan in a Gantt chart, trying to itemize all activities required as much as possible to ease the monitoring of the WP progress by the task leaders, WP leader and Project Coordinator. The WP annual plans will be delivered to the Project Coordinator during the first month of **every reporting year**, using the “Sending Docs form WP9-Task 9.1” available in A2C platform.

12.2 TASK STATUS REPORTS

These reports are required by the Project Coordinator to monitor the progress of the project. Each partner will contribute, sending details on the progress in their own activities to the respective Task leader.

Annex B presents the template each **task leader** is required to use for the Task Status report and instructions on how to complete it. The template includes, besides all the activities carried out, any deviation or change of what was planned, issues that may come up, results and achievements and the risks identification and analysis.

Task leaders will produce an annual Task Status Report that will be **quarterly updated** and discussed in the quarterly WP meetings. The **Task leaders** will upload the first version of the report, using the “Sending Docs Form” available in the A2C platform, to the corresponding WP and task, version that will be quarterly updated online.

12.3 ADMINISTRATIVE AND FINANCIAL COORDINATION

The project manager is responsible for the administrative and financial coordination of the project, and will compare the budget execution planning with the financial situation and degree of execution.

Budget execution planning (BEP) must be carried out in order to be able to manage the budget with the minimum margin of error. Once the GANTT schedule and the budget are known, the planning consists of linking both of them in order to be clear about the cost to be incurred in each period.

There are cost items that will be distributed throughout the execution of the project:

* Personnel.

* Amortization.

* Subcontracting in some cases.

There are other cost items that are carried out at a specific time:

* Purchase of materials.

* Travel.

* Publications.

* Subcontracting.

It is mandatory for the partners to draw up this planning in order to be able to analyse and manage the correct execution of the budget and to anticipate possible deviations so that we can act accordingly.

A technically correct execution of the project will lead to a logical distribution of the costs incurred.

The project manager will send a specific template to the partners that must be filled in and uploaded via form every 6 months.

Statement of financial situation

It is important that each partner analyses each cost item in the budget and establishes a cost estimate over the life of the project, i.e., indicate for each time period (month or duration of each task or package) what costs will be incurred.

This is the best starting point to achieve traceability between the technical development and the execution of the associated cost.

The model, to be sent by each partner, of the statement of the financial situation is attached as ANNEX K.

A timetable will be established for sending the status of the costs incurred by each partner.

The project manager shall request a statement of costs incurred on a six-monthly basis. The file shall be sent in the following month as shown below:

Project	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36		
Financial control																																						
Delivery month																																						

- Closing date of the cost period
- Closing date of the interim report period.
- Closing date of the final report period.

Date to send the financial control.

Annex K is to be completed every six months to be sent to the coordinator.

It should be named with the name of the acronym of each partner and include the period to which it refers. Example. SFS-PARTNER_MM. xlsx

Where PARTNER is the acronym of the partner. MMYM month and YEAR OF SUBMISSION.

To be sent from the website: www.agro2circular.org. In the area "sending docs", in the area "beneficiary data and statement financial situation" and clicking on "Statement financial situation".

12.4 PROJECT PROGRESS INTERNAL AUDITS

After receiving the WP status reports and reviewing all the meeting minutes, **the project coordinator** will evaluate the progress of the project for scope and schedule control. This evaluation will be performed **on a quarterly basis** and recorded in the project progress internal audit report.

Control of scope: the project coordinator will compare the activities carried out, results and achievements expected or achieved with the objectives and milestones, to assure that they are aligned with the final goal defined into the official project documents (Grant Agreement), which is the commitment made with the EC.

Schedule control: The purpose of schedule control is to ensure that project tasks are carried out as scheduled and that project deadlines are met. The project coordinator will monitor the schedule and track the difference between planned, actual and forecast activities/deadlines. The time control is performed on three main items:

- Start date and duration of each Task.
- Deliverable deadlines.
- Milestone deadlines

In case of non-compliance, it will be identified and log as an issue, ensuring that it will be carried out as per the Issues Management Process, devising, agreeing and implementing corrective actions, together with the project management board, in case of significant or critical deviations. If any changes arise as part of adjustments to the project, these will be dealt with accordingly in the Project Change Management Process and added in the change log.

Project status checklist: the audit report will include an evaluation of the overall project status, with a score of execution compliance according to the Template in ANNEX J.

Cost control:

The objective is to check compliance with the budget and to analyse possible deviations in order to study each case and apply the necessary corrections.

Project progress internal audit report: the different activities, conclusions, metric and results of this internal audit will be recorded in a report, according to the template shown in ANNEX C.

12.5 MANAGEMENT OF ISSUES AND DECISIONS

12.5.1 Issues management

Issue management aims to ensure that issues that have a potential impact on project scope, time, cost, quality, risk, or EC satisfaction are assessed and acted upon. Relevant issues should be logged and followed-up in the Issue log.

Key decisions can be logged in a Decision Log, which brings visibility to decisions and accountability as to how and by whom they are taken, and to whom they should be communicated.

The issue management process for this project is a four-step process and falls under the responsibilities of the Project Coordinator who should execute the process when required throughout the project lifecycle.

Step 1: Issue Identification

The purpose of this step is to facilitate the identification and documentation of issues. Examples of issues that can arise in the project are:

- Disagreements on the interpretation of requirements.
- The consortium has difficulties achieving the set goals (e.g. in terms of time, resources or quality).
- Non-conformities or deviations identified by the project coordinator, the project manager or any member of the PMB.
- Risks identified in the Risk Log that have happened and therefore have changed from potential problems to actual problems.
- External effects that influence the project in a negative way.
- Many other reasons.

Issues can be identified/raised by any member of the Consortium throughout the project lifecycle, using different communication channels such as meetings, emails, reports, among others.

After receiving the issue information, the Project Coordinator registers the issue in the Issue Log, with an ID coding:

ILX where X is a consecutive number.

Issues can also be registered in the Issue Log by any member of the PMB and then validated by the PC. The Issue Log contains information to be fulfilled at this stage, such as the issue identifier, the issue category, the issue details and impact, the status of the issue, the name of the person that identified the issue and the date of identification, a template of the issue log can be found in ANNEX D.

Step 2: Issue Assessment and Action Recommendation:

When an issue arises, an initial assessment will be performed by the person who raised the issue and subsequently inform the project coordinator who will assign the detailed analysis of the issue to the proper member of the PMB This person will assess the issue and identify its root cause. Also, it will recommend a solution and detail the necessary steps, effort and resources involved. The assessment will consider dimensions like:

- WP, Task and Risk related to the issue.
- Impact: What are the possible consequences of this issue? Will it have contractual impacts?
- Urgency: How urgent is a solution to this issue? This will influence the speed and planning of the issue reporting and resolution.
- Size: Is it an issue that requires some effort/cost to solve, or is it best handled by immediate action?

This information will be documented in the Issue Log and then used as an input to request approval by the appropriate decision makers. The PC then will document the decisions in the Decision Log (ANNEX E).

Issues can generate new change requests and therefore the next steps may follow the project change management process.

Step 3: Actions Implementation: After issues are evaluated and the remediation actions approved, the WP leaders will incorporate these actions into the WP Annual work plan and the PC will update project related documentation such as Decision Log or Change Log.

Step 4: Issue Control: The purpose of this step is to monitor and control the issues identified during the project. The PC is responsible for updating the Issue Log, which can include adding new issues, updating issue status, updating remediation action details, modifying urgency, impact, and/or size levels based on changes in the project environment, etc. The PC will quarterly check the issue's status and report to the PMB in the quarterly meetings.

12.5.2 Conflict resolution

The WP Leaders will assume responsibility for operational decisions within their WP, whereas the GA will be responsible for decisions related to strategic developments of the project.

Conflict resolution through a five-step procedure:

- Step 1: Problem solving discussions and negotiations will generally take place during the ordinary and ad-hoc meetings between the relevant partners.
- Step 2: If no solution can be found then the partners concerned will inform the WP Leader, who will mediate between partners.
- Step 3: If no solution is achieved, then the WP Leader will inform the Project Coordinator who will mediate between partners.
- Step 4: If no solution is achieved, then The General Assembly will be required to hold an extraordinary meeting within 15 days.
- Step 5: If the conflict can still not be resolved or if it significantly affects the viability or scope of the project as a whole, then the Project Coordinator will seek advice from the EC Project Officers.

In serious situations the Project Coordinator will recommend that any parties in conflict conduct external mediation jointly funded by each party.

Quorum: The GA shall not decide on issues unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (including attendees joining by teleconference).

- Each of the Beneficiaries has one vote. Absent members are not entitled to vote or transfer votes.
- Decisions will be taken by a simple majority of votes with the Project Coordinator holding a casting vote in the event of a tie.
- All partners retain a veto right.

12.5.3 Decision making

General Assembly as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium.

The voting rules, quorum and veto rights are described in the Consortium Agreement, sections 6.2.3 and 6.2.4.

Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the Minutes has been accepted. Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if the Project Coordinator circulates to all Members of the Consortium Body a written document, which is then agreed by the defined majority (according to voting rules and quorum) of all Members of the Consortium Body. Such a document shall include the deadline for responses.

Decisions taken without a meeting shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days after written notification, no Member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson. The

decisions will be binding after the Project Coordinator sends to all Members of the Consortium Body a written notification of this acceptance.

12.6 MANAGEMENT OF THE PROJECT CHANGES

Project change management aims to bring transparency, accountability and traceability to all project changes implemented after the project scope and project plans have been baselined. It ensures that changes with a significant impact in any of the project dimensions (i.e. scope, time, cost, quality or risk) are properly assessed, agreed on and approved by the appropriate level of authority.

The project change management process defines the activities related to identifying, documenting, assessing, approving, prioritising, planning and controlling changes, and communicating them to the General Assembly. The change management process for this project is a five-step process and falls under the responsibilities of the **Project Coordinator** who should execute the process when required throughout the project lifecycle.

Step 1: Change Identification:

The purpose of this step is to facilitate the identification and documentation of change requests to project baselines as scope, requirements, deliverables, resources, costs, schedule, or quality characteristics. Changes can be requested (or identified and raised) throughout the project lifecycle by any member of the Consortium.

After receiving a change request, the Project Coordinator registers the requested change in the Change Log and makes sure the change request is described using the Change Request Form (ANNEX F).

A request for a change can be submitted formally via a Change Request Form, or can be identified and raised during meetings as a result of decisions, issues or risks. The Change Log contains information to be fulfilled at this stage, such as the change identifier, the name of the requestor, the date of identification, the change category (e.g. new requirement, issue or risk related, business, etc.), the change details and impact, and the status of the change.

Step 2: Change Assessment and Action Recommendation:

The purpose of this step is to assess a) whether this request is indeed a project change, b) to define the different options to meet this request, c) to assess the size of the identified change for each option defined in terms of the impact to the project objectives, quality, risk, schedule,

cost, effort, and the contract with the contractor, and d) to decide on a priority for the implementation of that change request.

After this assessment, the recommended action will be detailed with the necessary steps, deliverables, cost, timescale and resources involved. Be aware that the recommended action may be to reject the requested change. This information will be documented by the Project Coordinator in the Change Log, which is then used as an input to the formal change approval or rejection by the appropriate decision makers.

New changes can generate new risks, issues or quality requirements and therefore change assessment will include the assessment of current or new risks, issues and quality requirements. The design of the change implementation (action) will also impact cost, scheduling and resources assigned to the project, so all these dimensions will be assessed before change approval. It is important to bear in mind that a change may require an amendment that implies a considerable amount of administrative work that is costly and may delay the project.

Step 3: Change Approval

The purpose of this step is to achieve a decision regarding the approval or rejection of the change according to section 10.4.2. Changes classified with high size will always be communicated to the Project Officer.

There are four possible decisions to be considered: Approve, Reject, Postpone, or Merge the change request. The decision details are documented in the Change Log. Key decisions may also be logged in the Decision log. If the change request needs further information or clarification, it returns to the "Change Assessment and Action Recommendation" step.

Step 4: Change Implementation

For the approved or merged changes, the WP leaders will incorporate the actions related to these changes into the *WP annual work plans* and update project related documentation (e.g. *Risk Log*, *Issue Log*, *Decision Log*, *Quality Review Checklist* and *Deliverables Acceptance Checklist*, if applicable).

Step 5: Change Control

The purpose of this step is to monitor and control project changes, to be able to easily communicate them to the several decision layers of the project, for approval or status updates. The Project Coordinator will collect any changes to the project or related actions and control the status of each change management activity.

WP meetings will be used to revise the status of changes and related actions, and to identify new changes. The Project Coordinator is responsible for updating the *Change Log*, which can include adding new changes, updating change status, updating effort estimation, modifying size and/or priority levels based on changes in project environment, etc.

Additionally, the Project Coordinator will report periodically (quarterly) the status of project changes to the Project Management Board and, when adequate, to other project participants.

12.7 RISK MANAGEMENT

Risk management is an important part of the project management because it is a way of assuring the quality of the project, identifying possible lack of quality and proposing preventive measures, as well as a way of anticipating possible issues that could affect the proper execution of the project and the achievement of its objectives, by proposing contingency measures to prevent such events from occurring.

The project risk management process defines the activities to identify, assess, prioritise, manage and control risks. This process is divided into four steps (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Risk management process

12.7.1 Step 1: Risk Identification

Risks must be continuously identified throughout the project lifecycle; however, very early during the preparation of the project proposal, an initial list of foreseen risks was created which can be found in the Annex 1 (part A) section 1.3.5 of the Grant Agreement, where proposed mitigation and contingency actions have also been included. These already identified risks, together with those new risks identified during the project, will be recorded in the Risk Log, according to the template shown in ANNEX G, which contains the risks identifier, risk ID and short description, the risk category and owner, as well as strategies, actions and timing, all in order to facilitate the monitoring and control of all aspects of the risks. The Risk will be identified with an ID coding:

RLX where X is a consecutive number.

The risk identification is made through a systemic approach based on the project objectives, using different tools and techniques such as desk review, brainstorming or workshops/meeting, on the basis of the knowledge and experience of the partners.

The following risk categories have been included in the risk identification analysis: Management (M), Technical (T), External (E).

WP leaders and task leaders will be in charge of the risk identification of their WP, and it will be a point of review and discussion in the quarterly WP meetings.

12.7.2 Step 2 Risk assessment

As soon as a possible risk is identified, next step will be to assess the likelihood and impact of the identified risks in terms of their influence to the project objectives. This assessment is necessary before any risk response planning can be done.

Risks are assessed based on their likelihood of occurrence and the impact in project objectives. The product of their likelihood (L) and impact (I) defines the Risk Level, which is then used as a reference for their prioritisation and risk response development.

Risk level= L*I

The likelihood (L) is a numerical value denoting the estimate of the probability of the risk to occur. The possible values are:

3=High, 2=Medium, 1=Low

The impact (I) is numerical value denoting the severity of the risk's impact (in case it occurs).

The possible values are:

≥12=High, 7-11=Medium, <7=Low

The risk level threshold is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Risk Likelihood/Impact matrix

WP leaders and task leaders are responsible for the Risk assessment with the support of the technical manager.

12.7.3 Step 3: Risk Response Development

The purpose of this step is to select the best risk response strategy and identify and plan the actions to control the risks.

The selection of the risk response strategy will be based on the results of the risk assessment (risk level), the type of risk, on the effects on the overall project objectives (e.g. schedule and costs), as well as on the cost of the strategy and its benefits (cost/benefit analysis). The strategy (or strategies) selected for each risk are documented in the Risk Log.

Two strategies are considered as risk responses: reduce and avoid:

- Avoid: develop contingency plans in case the risk occurs.
- Reduce: risk mitigation or reduction through the proactive implementation of risk reduction activities.

The following table describes the risk response approach for this project:

Scenario	Risk Response Strategy
Very high impact and high or very high likelihood or high or very high impact and very high likelihood.	Avoid or implement an immediate reduction
All other risk levels.	Reduce

Specific actions to implement the strategy will be defined, described, scheduled and assigned by the WP leaders together with the technical manager, while a Risk Owner assumes the responsibility for its implementation. The specific actions will be approved by the Technical Committee.

Actions will detail concrete activities, milestones and deliverables and will be documented in the Risk Log, clearly identifying the target resolution date. These actions (at least the most effort/cost consuming ones) will be incorporated into WP annual work plans, to have a consolidated view of all project related activities.

12.7.4 Step 4: Risk Control

The purpose of this step is to monitor and control the implementation of the risk response activities while continuously monitoring the project environment for new risks or changes (e.g. probability and/or impact) in the risks already identified. The project coordinator will review the Risks Log every three months, but also revise it after the occurrence of any event that might have a significant impact on the project environment and hence the project risks. The updating of the Risk Log can include adding new risks or actions, updating the status of response activities, changing risk levels based on mitigation actions, changing the assignment of actions, etc.

The WP leaders will report periodically the status of the risk and any response activities to the Project Coordinator in the quarterly WP Status Reports (PM). Risk status will be included in the periodic report to the REA.

12.7.5 Risk Management Roles and Responsibilities

Risk identification	WP leaders & Task leaders
Risk assessment & response development	WP leaders & Task leaders Technical manager
Response development approval	Technical Committee
Risk action implementation	Risk owner
Risk control	Project coordinator

13 PROJECT OUTPUTS

13.1 REPORT FOR PAYMENT REQUEST

The project coordinator must submit to the REA the technical and financial reports, according to the following reporting periods:

- RP1: from month 1 to month 18 (Periodic Report)
- RP2: from month 19 to month 36 (Final Report)

The coordinator must submit the progress report within 30 days following the end of each reporting period and must be drawn up using the forms and templates provided in the electronic exchange system.

The content of the reports is explained in detail in the Grant Agreement, article 20, sections 20.3 and 20.4 (pages 32-33).

13.2 DELIVERABLES

Deliverable submission is an obligation according to the article 19 of the Grant Agreement. The project coordinator is responsible for submitting all deliverables at their due date according to the List of Deliverables shown in Annex I section 1.3.2 of the Grant Agreement (Pages 7-14). A public summary of the confidential deliverables within WP1-WP5 will be provided to the REA at the final reporting period, summarising /highlighting the important results.

13.2.1 General elaboration rules

The deliverables will be prepared according to the Deliverable Template (ANNEX H), in compliance with its format, logos, statements and disclaimers.

The deliverables must include an Executive Summary, an Introduction section outlining clearly the Purpose and Scope, and a Conclusion section.

In the phase of Deliverable elaboration, the following rules have to be taken into consideration:

- The executive summary will be a section no more than one page that summarizes the important points of the deliverable in a very clear and exhaustive way.
- Objectives have to be clear from the beginning.
- The document has to be concise: giving a lot of information clearly and in a few words; expressing what needs to be said without unnecessary words; avoiding useless lengthening.
- Synthesize, summarize and get to the point always.
- Pay attention to glaring typos, leaving the spell check active and reading once more the document before considering it as consolidated and ready to be checked by the reviewers.
- To avoid repeating contents already described in previous Deliverables or in the Grant Agreement (always use references for that).
- Any bibliographic citation has to be referenced, using a numeric type of citation such as IEEE.

Although there are no requirements on the minimum or maximum number of pages, each Deliverable should provide sufficient information to both the REA and external reviewers to assess the project progress and its results. Very long deliverables create several problems:

- They don't attract the reader.
- It is easier to lose the thread of thought and the fundamental concepts.
- Their revision requires a long time, and results in more comments that require further revisions.

Therefore, Deliverables have to be very concise about which content to include in the documents. The right size for a given Deliverable depends largely on the topic, the objective, etc., but as a general rule, it is considered reasonable that Deliverables should not exceed 30 pages. Annexes may be added.

Deliverable coding

Both the draft and final versions will be numbered according to the Deliverable number shown in to the List of Deliverables shown in Annex I section 1.3.2 of the Grant Agreement (Pages 7-14), adding the version code that will be V0.x for consecutive draft versions and V1.x for consecutive versions of the final edition (Table 4)

Table 4: Deliverable coding

CODE FOR DRAFT VERSIONS	Dx.yV0.z
CODE FOR FINAL EDITION VERSIONS	Dx.yV1.z

Deliverable preparation timing:

The first draft of the deliverable must be ready a month before its due date, for its peer review, and the final version must be sent to the project coordinator a week before its due date.

Storage

The project coordinator will store the final versions of the deliverables in the corresponding folder on the A2C platform and put them at the disposal of all members of the consortium for consultation. Public Deliverables will be published on the project website.

13.2.2 Roles and responsibilities

The following roles will be involved in the delicate process of Deliverable preparation:

Deliverable lead beneficiary:

For each Deliverable, as specified in the List of Deliverables shown in Annex I section 1.3.2 of the Grant Agreement (Pages 7-14), there is a “lead beneficiary” who is **the task leader**, and they are responsible for elaboration of the deliverable, upon materials and documents provided by other project partners. Lead beneficiaries are the main editors and lead the Deliverable production process, being the main responsible for the submission of the document in due time. They are also the main contact point with the other roles, being in charge of asking contributions to other involved partners, uploading the document to the right location in the project platform and notify the Project Coordinator (CETEC) that it is ready for starting the Quality Check. It is in charge of providing an update of the Deliverables progress and explanation on eventual expected delay to the Project Coordinator.

Once the peer review related comments are received (if any), the lead beneficiary has to ensure that such comments/requests have been indeed addressed (involving, if it is the case, also the contributors).

Deliverable contributor: participants in the production of the Deliverable by contributing with content and supporting the lead beneficiary in producing a high-quality document, addressing eventual reviewer comments and requests.

Coordinator: the project coordinator must submit to the EC the deliverables identified in Annex 1 of the grant agreement, in accordance with the timing and conditions set out in it.

13.3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PRODUCTS

Disseminated products are items that are developed in the course of the project, which may be of external use, being some of them not required by the GA. Examples of disseminated products are:

- Papers for publication, posters, brochures, press releases, newsletters;
- Project website;
- Project brochure;
- Non-deliverable software;
- Presentations and demonstrations.

The outreach manager will be in charge of the dissemination & communication products management & procedures.

All dissemination & communication activities must be notified to the outreach manager in advance, so that plans can be updated and the information to be shared validated in terms of confidentiality and quality.

As soon as any partner carries out a dissemination or communication activity, the specific form, available in A2C website, must be filled in, attaching the activity report with all relevant information, including metrics to assess the activity impact/audience. By using these forms, all dissemination & communication activities will be automatically logged in an updated list in an excel sheet.

CLICK ON THE COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION OR MEETINGS TO WHICH YOU WANT TO UPLOAD DOCUMENTATION

13.4 ARTEFACTS

As a result of the activities carried out for project management and quality management, several documents will be produced according to Table 5, where it is shown the naming code to be assigned to each document.

Table 5: Coding to name the artefacts

ARTEFACT	NAME CODING
Meeting agenda	A2C_AoM_Type of meeting_DDMMYY DD=Day MM= Month YY= Year Example: A2C_AoM_GA_200221
Meeting minutes	A2C_MoM_Type of meeting_DDMMYY DD=Day MM= Month YY= Year Example: A2C_MoM_WP2_170322
Task Status report	A2C_SR_TaskX.Y_YY YY= Year Example: A2C_SP_Task9.1_21
Project Status Checklist	A2C_PSchecklist_MMY MM= Month YY= Year
Project progress internal audit report	A2C_IAR_MMY MM= Month YY= Year Example: A2C_IAR0222
Change Request Form	Change_Request_Form_DDMMYY
Quality review checklist	A2C_QRchecklist_MMY MM= Month YY= Year
E-mail subject	A2C_WPXX_Subject
WP Annual Work Plan	A2C_AWP_XX_YY XX= WP number YY= year
Deliverable draft	D.X.Y.V0.Z X.Y= deliverable number 0.Z=draft version
Final version of deliverables	D.X.Y.V1.Z X.Y= deliverable number 1.Z= Deliverable version

14 QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Project quality management aims to ensure that the project will meet the expected results in the most efficient way and that deliverables will be accepted by the REA. It involves overseeing

all activities needed to maintain a desired level of excellence. This includes creating and implementing quality assurance, as well as quality control.

14.1 QUALITY ASSURANCE

Quality Assurance (QA) is the activity of providing the evidence needed to establish the quality of work and therefore provide enough confidence that the project will satisfy the desired scope and objectives. Activities that are part of the quality assurance are:

- The activities involved in the monitoring and control of the project performance, explained in section 10; communication activities, control of scopes and schedule by internal audits, issue management, and risk management.
- The assurance of the quality of the deliverable via internal peer review.

14.2 DELIVERABLE QUALITY ASSURANCE

Project Deliverables are the major instruments to demonstrate both to the EC and external reviewers the project's progress, if the activities described in the Grant Agreement have been successfully carried out and if the objectives have been reached.

For guaranteeing that such important documents are successfully completed, satisfactorily understood and meet the objectives within the prescribed period, in order to obtain their formal acceptance, the Consortium needs to establish a Quality Procedure before shipment to the REA.

This quality procedure involved three different activities, the preparation of a deliverable review plan, the deliverable peer review and the monitoring of the process.

14.2.1 Deliverable review plan

The project coordinator will prepare a plan for the deliverables peer review at the beginning of the project. The plan will be prepared taking into consideration the partners expertise and their workload during the period of revision. The plan will include two internal reviewers per deliverable. All members of the consortium will take part in the deliverable review, and the plan will be shared with all the members before approval, in order to incorporate any suggestion or change. The coordinator will send a reminder to the partners involved a month before a period of deliverables review and submission, in this moment, if any of the reviewers has a good reason why they cannot perform the review, they must notify the project coordinator so that she could rearrange the revision plan.

14.2.2 Deliverable Internal Peer Review

As part of the quality assurance, internal reviews of the deliverables will take place for each Deliverable. The procedure will be as follows:

1. **Task leader** (lead beneficiaries) will upload the draft for review, by using the form “Sending Docs” in A2C website, selecting the corresponding WP folder, attaching the draft in a word format, with a **deadline of 1 month before the deliverables submission due date**. The draft version before reviewing will be v0.1, the version uploaded for reviewing will be v0.2. The project coordinator will notify the reviewers when the deliverable draft has been uploaded.
2. The review will be carried out online on the draft version v0.2 uploaded by the editor (lead beneficiary), where **reviewers** will suggest edits or add comments with the tool “Review suggested edit”, keeping track of who is making the suggested editions or comments. **The due time for this first review will be a week from the date of the draft uploading.**
3. As soon as the reviewers finish the review task, they will notify the task leader, who will accept or reject the proposed changes together with the reviewers, creating a new version v.0.3. This new version will be accepted or changed into new versions until the consolidated version is accepted by the internal reviewers, for considering the document qualitatively satisfactory, the internal reviewers will inform the WP leader when the version is satisfactory. The WP leader will track the process to make sure that **the final version of the deliverable is ready a week before the submission due date**. When the iterations require too much time and the deadline is close, the Project Coordinator will inform the PO in advance about the delay and will schedule together a new deadline, justifying this deviation into the Technical Report in due time.
4. The project coordinator and WP leader will check that info found in Deliverables are in line with DoA and with information found in WP status reports.
5. Deliverables that meet the acceptance criteria are formally accepted by the Project Coordinator, and sent to the REA.

14.2.3 Deliverable review roles and responsibilities

Draft editing for reviewing	Lead beneficiary & deliverable contributors
Preparation of the folder and form for the draft deliverables uploading	Project coordinator
Draft uploading on A2C drive	Lead beneficiary
Notification to the internal reviewers that the draft is ready for review	Project coordinator

Quality review of the deliverables	Internal reviewers assigned by the project coordinator in the deliverable review plan
Tracking of all the process of deliverable peer review, what version is consolidated, and assurance that the deadlines are met	WP leader
Assurance that the deliverable content is aligned with the WP status reports	Project coordinator and WP leader
Acceptance of the deliverable final version to be submitted to the REA	Project coordinator

14.3 QUALITY CONTROL

The purpose of this step is to monitor and consolidate results from the quality assurance activities in order to assess compliance and performance of these activities, recommend necessary changes, and plan new or refine existing quality assurance activities. Quality monitoring & controlling is performed throughout the project by the Project Coordinator.

The Quality Review Checklist (ANNEX 24) will be used by the Project Coordinator for evaluating the quality control activities and to validate compliance with the plans in terms of scope, time, cost, quality, project organization, communication, risks, and EC satisfaction.

This checklist includes the assessment of the quality compliance of the following areas:

1. Scope
2. Schedule
3. Cost
4. Quality
5. Risk
6. Issues & decisions
7. Communication
8. Project organization
9. REA satisfaction

15 ANNEX A: MEETING AGENDA AND MINUTES TEMPLATES

Meeting Agenda

Meeting Title:		Meeting Date/Time:	
Meeting Type:		Meeting Location:	
Meeting Coordinator:		Issue Date:	

Participant Name <i>(invited)</i>	Organisation / Email

Meeting Objectives
1.

Agenda Items	Time	Owner

Related Documents	Location
XYZ.doc	U:\ProjectX\Documents\

Minutes of Meeting

Meeting Title:		Meeting Date/Time:	
Meeting Type:		Meeting Location:	
Meeting Coordinator:		Issue Date:	

Attendee Name	Initials	Present	Organisation / Email
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
		<input type="checkbox"/>	

Meeting Agenda
<i><A summary of the meeting agenda, e.g. meeting objectives and agenda items.></i>

Meeting Summary
<i><Outline points discussed and outcomes for the meeting></i>

Decisions taken			
Decision Id	Description	Date of Decision Taken	Decision Owner
		<i>dd/mm/yy</i>	

Action Id	Description	Target Resolution Date	Owner
		<i>dd/mm/yy</i>	<i>Initials</i>

Proposed Agenda for Next Meeting	Proposed Next Meeting Date:
<i>List potential agenda items of the next meeting</i>	

Related Documents	Location
XYZ.doc	U:\ProjectX\Documents\

16 ANNEX B WP STATUS REPORT TEMPLATE

SR_WPX_TaskX.Y_Year

WP Status Report

Identification: (SR_WPX_TaskX.Y_Year)

Title:

Task Leader:

1. Aims & Objectives of activities undertaken during the Quarter

1-3 months	
4-6 months	
6-9 months	
10-12 months	

13-15 months	
16-18 months	
19-21 months	
22-24 months	

25-27 months	
28-30 months	
31-33 months	
34-36 months	

Please describe activities compared to the initial planning.

2. Activities undertaken & partners involved during the reporting period

1-3 months	
4-6 months	
6-9 months	
10-12 months	

13-15 months	
16-18 months	
19-21 months	
22-24 months	

25-27 months	
28-30 months	
31-33 months	
34-36 months	

Please describe next quarter’s proposed activities

3. Activities to be undertaken & partners involved during the next reporting period

1-3 months	
4-6 months	
6-9 months	
10-12 months	

13-15 months	
16-18 months	
19-21 months	
22-24 months	

25-27 months	
28-30 months	
31-33 months	
34-36 months	

Indicate changes in project action**4. Issues arising during the quarter**

1-3 months	
4-6 months	
6-9 months	
10-12 months	

13-15 months	
16-18 months	
19-21 months	
22-24 months	

25-27 months	
28-30 months	
31-33 months	
34-36 months	

5. Please outline any change or corrective/contingency actions required

1-3 months	
4-6 months	
6-9 months	
10-12 months	

13-15 months	
16-18 months	
19-21 months	
22-24 months	

25-27 months	
28-30 months	
31-33 months	
34-36 months	

6. Project Deliverables Status

Output/Action /Sub-action	Description	% completed

7. Risk Identification and analysis

Risk description	Rank (Low/Medium/High)	Mitigation & Contingence measures

8. Innovation: IP/Results

RESULTS	Description	Exploitable/not exploitable

17 ANNEX C PROJECT PROGRESS

INTERNAL AUDIT REPORT TEMPLATE

A2C_IAR_MMY.Y.V0

Internal audit Report

1.1 Milestones and Deliverables

ID	Milestone	Target Delivery Date	Actual Delivery date	Status	Comments
				<on-going, planned, achieved >	

<The deliverable IDs should be aligned with the ones used previously in the DoA.>

1.2 Project Plan (per Work Package)

Activity	Planned		Audit period		Performance			
	Start Date	End Date	Start Date	End Date	Scope		Schedule	
					R1 (%)	R2 (%)	D1 (%)	D2 (%)

R1= Ratio (%)= Progress/Project plan

R2= Ratio (%)= Progress/Annual plan

D3= Delay (month) compared to project plan

D4= Delay (month) compared to annual plan

Nov2021

Internal audit report template.V0

1 / 4

<This section is to be fulfilled for the key Work Packages (WP), if a considerable cost is involved or the effort is greater than 20 workdays (WDs)>

<Work Package #[...] and name description>										
Planned		Actual		Total Planned Effort at Completion ¹	Planned Effort ²	Actual Effort ²	Progress (Earned Value) ³	Performance		
Start Date	End Date	Start Date	End Date					Schedule ⁴	Budget ⁵	
				<1000€>	<500€>	<300€>	<400€>	<80% >	<133% >	

Also known as Budget at Completion (BAC).

² The quantification of effort should be measured until the end of last week.

³ Earned value=Planned effort*% of completion

⁴ Ratio= Progress / Planned effort/ *100 (R<100%= ; R>100%=)

⁵ Ratio= Progress /Actual effort * 100 (R<100%= ; R>100%=)

¹ Also known as Budget at Completion (BAC).

² The quantification of effort should be measured until the end of last week.

³ Earned value=Planned effort*% of completion

⁴ Ratio= Progress / Planned effort/ *100 (R<100%; R>100%=-)

⁵ Ratio= Progress /Actual effort * 100 (R<100%; R>100%=-)

1.3 Budget and Costs

<This section is only applied for yearly reporting.

It should allow the reader to know the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) of the project for the full lifecycle. As a consequence, costs beyond the reporting period should also be identified...>

Expenditure	2021		2022		2023		202d		202e		Total cost
	Budget Line	Amount									
Equipment (k€)											
Personnel (k€)											
Consumables (k€)											
Travel (k€)											
Publications (k€)											
Subcontracting (k€)											
Total per year (k€)											

r

1.4 Arised issues

WP	TASK	Issue Description

1.5 Proposed changes

WP	TASK	Change Description

1.6 Identified risk

WP	TASK	Risk Description

1.7 Achievements

Project Highlights / Achievements	Comments

1.8 Score of the project status checklist

1.9 Results of the quality checklist

1.10 Audit Conclusions

1.11 Audit performed by

2 APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

<Use this section to reference (or append if needed in a separate annex) any relevant or additional information. Specify each reference or related document by title, version (if applicable), date, and source (e.g. the location of the document or the publishing organisation).>

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	<i><Example of a related document> <04.Project_Handbook.XYZ.11-11-2017.V.1.0.docx></i>	<i><Example of a location> < U:\METHODS\ProjectX\Documents\></i>
2	Project folder	<i><Insert project folder location.></i>
3		

18 ANNEX D ISSUE LOG TEMPLATE

Issue Identification and Description					
ID	WP/Task/Risk	Description	Status	Identified By	Identification Date
<i>Guidelines</i>	<i><Issues can be organised in different categories such as Business, Staffing, Contractor, Legal ...></i>	<i><Description of the issue, including how it came about (known risk, unknown risk, ...) and its impact on the project.></i>	<i><Status for the issue: One of the following values: - Open - Postponed - Resolved - Closed></i>	<i><The name of the Person who identified the issue></i>	<i><Date when the issue was raised or was identified <dd/mm/yy>></i>
IL01					
IL02					
IL03					
IL04					
IL05					
IL06					
IL07					
IL08					
IL09					

19 ANNEX E DECISION LOG TEMPLATE

A2C_Decision log_Template V.0

Decision Log

Decision Identification						Ownership			Decision Implementation	
ID	Title	Description	Identified by	People present	Comments	Decision Owner	Decision Date	Escalation	Application Date	Decision communicated to:
Guidelines	<i><Short title for the decision.></i>	<i><Description of the decision details and impact, if applicable.></i>	<i><The name of the person who identified the need for a decision.></i>	<i><Log the names of the people present when the decision was made.></i>	<i><- ID for related changes in the change log. - ID for the related risk in the Project Plan - ID for related issues.></i>	<i><The name of the person accountable for the decision.></i>	<i><Date on which the decision was taken.></i>	<i><Should the decision be escalated to the GA? (Yes) or (No).></i>	<i><Date on which the decision becomes applicable.></i>	<i><The groups, teams and individuals to whom the decision needs to be communicated.></i>
D01										
D02										
D03										
D04										
D05										
D06										
D07										
D08										
D09										
D10										
D11										
D12										
D13										
D14										
D15										
D16										
D17										
D18										
D19										
D20										

<These notes should be deleted in the final version.>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

20 ANNEX F CHANGE LOG AND CHANGE REQUEST FORM

A2C_Change_log_Template v.0

Change Log

Change Identification and Description						Change Assessment and Action Description				Change Approval				Change Implementation	
ID	Title	Description	Status	Request ed by	Date Identified	Action Details (effort & responsible)	Size (Effort)	Priority	Target Delivery Date	Escala tion	Decisi on	Decid ed by	Decision Date	Actual Delivery Date	Traceability and Comments
Guidelines	<Short title for the requested change.>	<More detailed description of the requested change including the possible impact of not implementing the change.>	<Status for the change. Use the following values (not exhaustive):> - Submitted - Assessing - Approved - Rejected - Postponed	<The name of the person who requested the change.>	<The initial submission date of the change request (dd/mm/yy)>	<Description of the recommended action(s), including steps, deliverables, timescale, resources and effort involved.>	<A numerical value denoting how much effort will be necessary to implement the change.>	<A numerical value denoting the agreed priority of the change: 5- Very High to >	<Target date for the change to be delivered: (dd/mm/yy)>	<Should the issue be escalated to the Directing or Steering Layers? (Yes) or (No)>	<Describe the decision taken. Possibly link with the item in the decision log.>	<Person or Committee that approved or rejected the change.>	<Date on which the decision was made: (dd/mm/yy)>	<Date on which the change was actually delivered: (dd/mm/yy)>	<Related artefacts:> - ID for the related tasks in the Project Work Plan - ID for related Risks, issues and decisions. - Plus any additional information or comments related to the issue.>
C01															
C02															
C03															
C04															
C05															
C06															
C07															
C08															
C09															
C10															
C11															
C12															
C13															
C14															
C15															
C16															
C17															
C18															
C19															
C20															

<These notes should be deleted in the final version.>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

A2C_Change_Request_Form_DDMMYY

Change Request Form

WP/TASK	<WP&Task-ID>	Change-ID	<link-to-the-change-log>
Change-Request			
Change-Title		Identification-Date	<dd/mm/yyyy>
Requested-by	<The-name-of-the-requestor/group>	Category	
Priority	<input type="checkbox"/> Very-High <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Very-Low		
Change-Description-&-Details			
<The-purpose-of-this-form-is-to-capture-the-need-and-characteristics-of-a-project-change-request. The change-request-is-the-first-step-of-the-change-request-process. Once-the-change-request-is-logged-into-the-Change-Log, then-this-form-is-updated-with-the-assigned-Change-ID-and-the-form-is-archived.>			
Current-Situation:			
<Describe-the-current-situation-(a-problem, an-opportunity-or-a-new-need—why-is-there-a-need-for-a-change-in-the-project?)>			
Desired-Situation:			
<Describe-the-desired-situation. What-is-the-goal-and-benefits-of-this-change-request?>			
Impact-or-Risks:			
<Describe-the-impact-or-risks-of-not-implementing-this-change. If-this-impact-or-risks-can-be-quantified, then-this-can-help-with-the-analysis-(cost-benefit-analysis)-and-final-decision-regarding-the-implementation-(or-not)-and-the-priority-of-this-change.>			
Out-of-Scope:			
<Clarify-what-is-out-of-the-scope-of-this-change-request. This-clarifies-further-the-boundaries-of-the-requested-change-and-ensures-that-only-the-needed-change-is-implemented.>			
References-and-Related-Documents		Location	
XYZ.doc		U:\ProjectX\Documents\	

21 ANNEX G RISK LOG TEMPLATE

A2C_Risk log_Template V0

Risk Log

Risk Identification and Description						Risk Assessment					Risk Response				
ID	Category	W/P/TASK	Description	Status	Identified By	Identificati on Date	Likelihood (L)	Impact (I)	Risk Level (L*I)	Risk Owner	Escalation	Risk Response Strategy	Action Details (effort & responsible)	Target Date	Traceability/Comments
Guidelines	«Risks can be organised in different categories such as Management (M), Technical (T), External (E)»	«W/P/TASK ID»	«Description of the risk including its causes, the kinds of problems that could result (potential effects), and risk dependencies.» «Because of (CONDITION), it might be that (EVENT), which will lead to (IMPACT).»	«Status for the risk. One of the following values: - Proposed - Awaiting for Approval - Approved - Rejected - Closed»	«The name of the Person who identified the risk.»	«Date when the risk was identified {dd/mm/yyyy}»	«A numerical value denoting the probability that the risk will occur. 5- Very High to 1- Very Low»	«A numerical value denoting the severity of the risk's impact. 5- Very High to 1- Very Low»	«Product of the two previous columns: $RL = L * I$ »	«Name of the person accountable for managing and monitoring the risk.»	«The issue to be escalated to the Technical manager or Technical Committee.»	«Strategy for managing the risk: - Avoid - Reduce»	«Description of the mitigation action(s), including the objective, scope, deliverables, the person responsible and the estimated effort needed.»	«Date on which the risk response is expected to be implemented.»	«Related artefacts: - ID for the related mitigation tasks in the Project Plan - ID for related changes, issues or decisions (log entries).»
RL01															
RL02															
RL03															
RL04															
RL05															
RL06															
RL07															

22 ANNEX H DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

D8.1 – Title of the deliverable

December 2021

Authors: Author1 (Partner short name); Author2 (Partner short name)

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A2C – Deliverable DX.XVx.x

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1 Technical references

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Coordinator Name PARTNER NAME coordinator@mail@partner.eu
Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)

Deliverable No.	D#.#
Dissemination level*	
Work Package	WP # - WP Title
Task	T#.# - Task Title
Lead beneficiary	Partner number (partner short name)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	Partner number (partner short name), Partner number (partner short name), Partner number (partner short name)
Due date of deliverable	DD Month 201Y
Actual submission date	DD Month 201Y

- * PU = Public
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1		First draft of document
v0.x		Revised version based on the comments of Name Reviewer(s) - Organisation
v1.0		First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v1.1		First draft based upon first final version
v2.0		Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

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Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1		

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader		
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator		

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

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Disclaimer

This document reflects only the views of the author(s) the European Research Executive Agency (REA) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the A2C consortium shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused.

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4 Glossary 6

5 Executive summary <abstract> 7

6 <Sections decided by the author> 8

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8 ANNEXES 10

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2.2 List of Figures

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23 ANNEX I QUALITY CHECK LIST TEMPLATE

Quality review checklist_TemplateV.0

Project Quality Review			
Project Quality Reviewer:	<Name of the person performing the		
Review Date:	<dd/mm/yyyy>		
Overall Score:	0%		
Overall Project Quality Assessment			
Area	% of Quality Compliance	Score	Included?
Scope		0%	Yes
Schedule		0%	Yes
Cost		0%	Yes
Quality		0%	Yes
Risk		0%	Yes
Issues & Decisions		0%	Yes
Communication		0%	Yes
Project Organisation		0%	Yes
IEA Satisfaction		0%	Yes
Scoring Legend:			
0	"No answer: nothing done."		
5	"Yes, Partially" answer: some work done, but not to the required/expected level.		
10	"Yes" answer. Meets requirements and expectations as per the PM² methodology.		
1 to 10	The questions started by "How well...?" should be answered by scoring the related activity from 1 to 10, meaning that 1 is "very poor", 5 is "average" (requirements are met) and 10 is "excellent" (material that can be referenced).		
N/A	This check is not applicable to this		
Overall Assessment Key:			
	Critical /significant issues or major process non-compliance.		
	Unless immediate action is taken, project may become red.		
	No significant non-compliance foreseeable at this time.		

Quality Review Checklist

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Quality review checklist_TemplateV.0

Quality Review Checklist

< This table should be used for documenting findings and recommendations on quality assurance and control activities, the plan is adequate to resolve the identified findings.>

ID	Findings	Impact	Recommendation	Action Details (effort & responsible)
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				
8				
9				
10				

Scope Management		% of Quality Compliance	0%	
		Answer	Score	Comments
Scope Planning				
1	Can the project deliverables be easily tracked from the Project Work plans?	No	0	
2	Has the project scope been clearly understood and agreed by the consortium s in the Planning Kick-off meeting?	No	0	
3	Is the Project Coordinator comfortable with the project plans?	No	0	
Scope Change Control				
4	Is a documented change management process in place?	No	0	
5	Is a Project Change Management Plan documented?	No	0	
6	Is a Change Log maintained?	No	0	
7	Is the Change Log reviewed regularly?	No	0	
8	Are Change Control Meetings in place?	No	0	
9	Is an escalation procedure for project changes documented and being followed?	No	0	
10	Were all scope changes approved by the general assembly?	No	0	
		0	0	

Cost		% of Quality Compliance	0%	
		Answer	Score	Comments
Cost control				
1	Are costs being actively managed?	No	0	
2	Is the "percentage completed" (based on duration) accurate?	No	0	

Schedule		% of Quality Compliance	0%	
		Answer	Score	Comments
Activity Definition				
1	Is there a Project Work Plan (WBS+effort & cost estimations+project schedule)?	No	0	<Add here the justification for the answer given.>
2	Is there a consolidated schedule (Gantt chart)?	No	0	
3	Can you link the activities back to WBS?	No	0	
4	Is the level of detail (granularity) of the schedule appropriate?	No	0	
5	Are relevant business implementation related activities on the schedule?	No	0	
6	Are relevant project management activities on the schedule?	No	0	
7	Do tasks / activities have documented start and end events?	No	0	
8	Does all work activities have a measurable output?	No	0	
Schedule Control				
1	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	No	0	
2	Is the schedule regularly updated with actual velocity?	No	0	
3	Is project on track regarding schedule ?	No	0	
4	Is the schedule reviewed regularly to consider project changes?	No	0	
5	Is the critical path reviewed regularly?	No	0	
6	Are resources allocation checked regularly?	No	0	
7	Are all the resources with the right amount of work (not over-allocated)?	No	0	
8	Are internal and/or subcontractor resources delivering results per plan?	No	0	
9	Are there regular reviews with internal and/or subcontractor resources?	No	0	
10	Are project management processes being used with internal and subcontractor resources?	No	0	
		0	0	

Quality		% of Quality Compliance	0%	
		Answer	Score	Comments
Quality Assurance				
1	Is the configuration management procedure being executed?	No	0	
2	Is a project repository being maintained?	No	0	
3	Is the project repository up to date?	No	0	
4	Is the project considering a Project Quality Assurance (PQA) team/person?	No	0	
5	Is quality being measured independently?	No	0	
6	Are deliverables meeting their acceptance criteria?	No	0	
7	When completed, have deliverables been accepted & signed-off?	No	0	
8	Were the previous review recommendations implemented?	No	0	
9	Was a deliverables peer review conducted?	No	0	
10	Are project plans regularly reviewed by the coordinator?	No	0	
11	Have audits been performed by the coordinator?	No	0	
Quality Control				
12	Are quality control activities taking place?	No	0	
13	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	No	0	
14	Are project quality reviews following the planned frequency and activities?	No	0	
15	Are security & business continuity activities performed?	No	0	
16	Is there a project configuration log?	No	0	

Risk		% of Quality Compliance		0%	
		Answer	Score		
Risk Identification					
1	Is there a Risk Management Plan?	No	0		<i>(Add here the justification for the answer)</i>
2	Were risks identified for this project?	No	0		
3	Is a Risk Log being used in the project?	No	0		
4	Are requestor side and provider side involved in risk identification, including the Project Core	No	0		
5	Are the identified risks belonging to more than one risk category?	No	0		
Risk Assessment					
6	Were risks quantified in terms of their risk level (likelihood & impact)?	No	0		
7	Is risk assessment data accurate?	No	0		
8	Is the risk impact on project budget assessed?	No	0		
9	Were all the risks approved as defined in the escalation procedure?	No	0		
10	Were all the high and very high risks (risk level > 15) approved by the Project Steering Committee (PSC)?	No	0		
11	Do you have a plan how to fund the risk actions?	No	0		
Risk Response Development					
12	Are all high and very high risks avoided or immediately reduced?	No	0		
13	Are risk response strategies selected for each approved risk?	No	0		
14	Are contingency plans defined for accepted risks?	No	0		
15	Are the actions related to the risk response strategies incorporated in the Project Work Plan?	No	0		
Risk Monitor & Control					
16	Is the Risk Log frequently revisited (at least weekly)?	No	0		
17	Are risks discussed in Project Follow-up (WP Meetings)?	No	0		
18	Are risks discussed in Project TA Meetings?	No	0		
19	Are risks discussed in Project Review GA Meetings?	No	0		
20	Are risks discussed in Project PMB Meetings?	No	0		
21	Are risks reviewed regularly (identification of new risks, assessment of the risk level and effectiveness of implemented actions)?	No	0		
22	Is the risk log reviewed when changes are approved?	No	0		
23	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	No	0		

Issues & Decisions		% of Quality Compliance		0%	
		Answer	Score	Comments	
Issue Identification and Description					
1	Is an issue management process in place?	No	0	<Add here the justification for the answer given.>	
2	Is there an Issue Management Plan?	No	0		
3	Is an Issue Log being used in the project?	No	0		
5	Is a Decision Log being used in the project?	No	0		
Issue Assessment and Action Description					
6	Are issues assessed in terms of urgency, impact and size?	No	0		
7	Is issue assessment data accurate?	No	0		
8	Is the effort of the issue-related action properly assessed?	No	0		
9	Are actions selected for each issue?	No	0		
10	Is a escalation procedure clearly defined for issues (based on urgency, impact and size)?	No	0		
11	Are issue owners assigned to actions?	No	0		
12	Are decisions following the defined escalation procedures for issues, risks and changes?	No	0		
Issue Monitor & Control					
13	Is the Issue Log reviewed at appropriate intervals?	No	0		
14	How well is issues status monitored & reported?	No	0		
15	Is the team closing issues in suitable time?	No	0		
16	Is there any follow-up done on late items?	No	0		

Communication		% of Quality Compliance	0%	
		Answer	Score	Comments
Communications Planning				
1	Is there a project contacts list ?	No	0	<Add here the justification for the answer given.>
2	Does a Communications Management Plan exist?	No	0	
3	Are the expected project meetings and reports documented?	No	0	
4	Is the Communications Management Plan including all partners?	No	0	
5	Are the main partners comfortable with the communication plan?	No	0	
Information Distribution				
6	Was an internal kick-off meeting conducted?	No	0	
7	Is project status communicated to partners according to the Communication Plan?	No	0	
8	Are Project WP Meetings happening regularly?	No	0	
9	Are there regular GA meetings?	No	0	
10	Was an external kick-off meeting conducted?	No	0	
11	Are all meetings happening as planned?	No	0	
Performance Reporting				
12	Are meeting minutes published after meetings?	No	0	
13	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	No	0	
Escalation Management				
14	Is a documented escalation process in place & understood?	No	0	
15	Is it being used effectively?	No	0	
16	Were escalation results been satisfactory(if any)?	No	0	

Project Organisation		% of Quality Compliance	0%	
		Answer	Score	Comments
Organization & Planning				
1	Are project roles & responsibilities defined and documented?	No	0	<Add here the justification for the answer given.>
2	Is there a Project Organization chart with all interfaces?	No	0	
Team Development				
3	Is the level of cooperation between teams satisfactory for the Project Coordinator?	No	0	
4	Were teamwork issues handled correctly?	No	0	
5	How satisfied are the team members with the project (scale: 0 lowest - 10 highest)?	0	0	

REA Satisfaction (Scale: 0 lowest - 10 highest)		% of Quality Compliance	0%	
		Answer	Score	Comments
1	How satisfied is the REA with the schedule (allowing for Change Requests)?	0	0	<Add here the justification for the answer given.>
2	How satisfied is the REA with requirements?	0	0	
3	How satisfied is the REA with the quality of deliverables?	0	0	
4	How satisfied is the REA with project communication?	0	0	
5	How satisfied is the REA with the technical ability of the consortium?	0	0	
6	What is the overall REA satisfaction?	0	0	

24 ANNEX J PROJECT STATUS CHECKLIST

A2C_Project Status Checklist_TemplateV0

Project Status Checklist
PSchecklistMMXXv0

Executing Phase Checks List			Date:	dd/mm/yyyy
			% of Phase Compliance	0%
#	Description	Answer	Score	Comments
1	Are resources and budget available to complete activities and to transfer deliverables to the requestor side?	No	0	<Add a justification here.>
2	Have activities been performed as defined and scheduled in the Project Work Plan?	No	0	
3	Were artefacts produced, updated and revised as planned?	No	0	
4	Were the quality assurance and control activities performed as planned?	No	0	
5	Have deliverables been tested / reviewed?	No	0	
6	Are tests results, issues and corrective actions documented?	No	0	
7	Are all major risks mitigated?	No	0	
8	Were security and data protection issues taken into account?	No	0	
9	Have all the approved changes been implemented?	No	0	
10	Are deliverables in line with requestor needs and expectations?	No	0	
11	Are all the project issues and corrective actions resolved / closed?	No	0	
12	Are draft deliverables on time for reviewing	No	0	
13	Were transition activities performed as planned?	No	0	
14	Have all the communication items (meetings, reports...) been implemented as planned?	No	0	
15	Did the REA formally approve deliverables (final approval)?	No	0	
16	Are deliverables reviews on time?	No	0	
17	Are deliverables ready for submission on time?	No	0	
18	Have all deliverables and artefacts been placed in the project repository?	No	0	
19	Is project configuration management effective?	No	0	
Total score for compliance		0	0	

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Assessment Key:	
	Major key activities for the phase(s) weren't performed (50% of the key activities or more are still to be completed).
	Some key activities are still to be completed before the phase(s) can be closed (% of compliance between 51% and 80%).
	Nearly all the key activities for the phase(s) are complete (more than 80% of the key activities). The decision to move to another

25 ANNEX K STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL SITUATION

6 Months	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total
PERSON/MONTH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PERSON COST	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
TRAVEL	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
EQUIPMENT	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
CONSUMABLES	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
PUBLICATIONS	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
OTHER COSTS	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
INDIRECT COST	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
SUBCONTRACTING	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
AUDIT COST	xxx	0,00 €	0,00 €							
TOTAL	0,00 €									

Please add comments about item costs

- * Personnel costs. Type of contract, Timesheets, Productive hours, Cost per Hour...etc.
- * Travel costs. Linked to the WP and justification.
- * Equipment. Linked to the WP and justification.
- * Consumables. Linked to the WP.
- * Publications. Linked to the WP and communication media.
- * Other costs. Linked to the WP and justification.
- * The audit costs is only for the partners with grnt up to 325,000€ and for the end of the project.

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